

Typology of Exercises for the Development of Coherent Speech

Abduvalieva Ominakhon

4th year student of the "Primary Education" direction at Namangan State University

Ulukhuzhaev Narzullokhon Ziyovadinovich

Professor, departments "Preschool and Primary Education" Namangan State University

email : nfuzulloxon56@mail.ru

Abstract: *The article examines issues related to the typology of exercises for developing coherent speech in native language lessons for primary school students. It provides a general description of the concept of "coherent speech", presents a typology of exercises used in native language lessons, and proposes a methodology for working with them.*

Keywords: *speech, coherent speech, utterance, text, meaning, exercise, typology, work system, didactics, superphrasal unity, methodology.*

Introduction

Coherent speech is a section that has always been singled out by methodologists as a special area of work on speech development. This is explained by the importance that coherent speech has in the life of a person and society.

From a linguistic point of view, coherent speech is "a section of speech that has a significant length and is divided into more or less complete independent parts." [1,64]

In the methodology, the concept of "coherent speech" is used in three meanings:

1. coherent speech is a process, an activity of a speaker, a writer (in this usage, for example: in the process of coherent speech, students master...);
2. the product, the result of this activity, the text, the statement (in such word usage, for example: analysis of coherent speech (student's statement);
3. the title of the section of work on speech development.

Since the terms "statement" and "text" are used as synonyms along with the term "connected speech", we will clarify their meaning.

An utterance in linguistics is a message, an act of communication, a unit of communication, a functional unit, etc. At the same time, some linguists classify only sentences as utterances, while others distinguish between utterances of different lengths (volumes), equal to the length of a sentence, the length of a superphase unity, the length of a paragraph, etc. [4,94]

Materials.

For methodologists, an utterance (like coherent speech) is both the speech activity of a student when he gives a detailed answer on the material of an academic discipline, orally or in writing reproduces the content of what he has read, writes an argument, a story, an article for a wall newspaper, etc., and the result of this activity: a detailed answer, a presentation (oral and written), an argument, a story, etc., i.e. a certain speech work, more than a sentence. [3,58]

In the system of work on the development and improvement of students' coherent speech, the correct choice of tasks that are accessible to a specific category of students is of great importance.

An exercise in didactics is defined as "a systematically organized repeated performance of an action (mental or practical) with the purpose of mastering it or improving its quality." From this definition it follows that exercises are designed to organize the reproductive (reproductive) activity of students, necessary for the development of skills and abilities. It is emphasized that "memorization and exercise - the two main methods usually used by a student at school to master educational material " - do not require "creative thinking from the student... And no matter what knowledge and skills we teach children, including reasoning skills," as a result of such training, the child becomes, as it were, an intellectual dependent, constantly served by the teacher." To develop the creative activity of students, it is proposed to use search, problem-solving, and creative tasks along with exercises. "Operating knowledge in new conditions is problem solving" [5].

In the process of speech activity, creativity is always present to one degree or another. Naturally, the methodology of speech development operates not only with exercises in the above sense, but also with tasks. However, due to the tradition that has developed in the methodology of the Russian language, different types of work that focus on both the reproductive and creative activities of students are indiscriminately called exercises. In this case, the typology of exercises acquires special significance [2].

Research and methods.

Of the various bases that can be taken into account when examining it, the most significant are the content, the assimilation of which the exercises are aimed at, and the method of activity of the students, predetermined by one or another type of task. An attempt to take into account each of these bases and to relate them to each other in a single typology of exercises inevitably leads to its complex organization.

Thus, on the first of the above-mentioned grounds, it is possible to construct a series of exercises applicable to the main areas of work on language tools in the aspect of speech development.

Exercises designed to master the norms of literary language.

Exercises aimed at enriching students' speech with synonymous (correlative) language tools.

The latter include:

- a) exercises aimed at developing the ability to select from a number of correlative linguistic means the most appropriate for expressing a given content of statements in accordance with the task and circumstances of speech;
- b) exercises aimed at developing the ability to adapt linguistic means to each other in a coherent statement.

Each of the indicated types of exercises, in turn, can be represented by a series of exercises, distinguished depending on what kind of norm, or what kind of synonymous series, or what kind of sphere of utterance is being discussed. [4].

Exercises aimed at mastering the same component of the work content differ in the way the students are engaged in the task. According to this feature, it is important to distinguish between exercises of a reproductive nature, which involve the students reproducing the knowledge and skills they have acquired in order to form, consolidate and improve their speech skills and abilities, and exercises of a productive nature, which involve the manifestation and development of elements of creative activity. It is necessary, however, to emphasize that in many cases it is impossible to draw a strict line between the above types of exercises (especially when the aspect of speech development is meant).

Most often, this boundary is drawn between exercises consisting in the analysis of ready-made linguistic material and exercises in the creation of an utterance or its elements. This approach, to a certain extent justified, cannot be elevated to an absolute, since the perception of someone else's utterance is one of the aspects of speech communication, in the act of which, to one degree or another, a creative principle is always present. The higher the level to which the considered unit of language belongs in its specific speech manifestation (cf.: word, phrase, sentence, text), the more elements of activity that are not amenable to simple reproduction of what has been learned are contained in its analysis. And yet, if we have in mind the same object of consideration (for example, a sentence or text), the analysis of a ready-made construction is simpler than the creation of one's own, since it frees one from a number of operations (such as, for example, the definition and logical organization of the content of the utterance, the selection of lexical material, etc.).

Results.

The arsenal of Russian language teaching methods includes a wide range of exercises that transition from the analysis of ready-made language material to the creation of one's own statements – these are various types of transformations of the original didactic material.

Without claiming to be an exhaustive list, we will indicate the main types of exercises of each of the named types:

I. Analysis of finished material.

Observations on specially prepared questions and tasks.

Selection (recognition) and characterization (analysis) of the necessary elements.

Comparison of comparable phenomena of language.

Analysis of the text from the point of view of the correlation of the linguistic means used in it and the task, conditions, and content of the statement.

II. Transformations of the given linguistic material.

Language experiment.

Synonymous replacements of these linguistic facts.

Construction of various language units (based on supporting elements and proposed models, diagrams).

Distribution of source material.

Compression of this construction.

Editing.

III. Creation of a statement (or its parts).

The choice of linguistic means or type of speech in accordance with the given topic and situation of the utterance.

Construction of elements of the statement taking into account the proposed speech situation.

Preparation of a plan and working materials for an essay on a given topic (in a specific or selected style of speech).

Creating fragments of an essay on a specific topic (in a given or selected style of speech).

An essay on a proposed or independently formulated topic in a certain style of speech [1 .147]

Discussion.

Speech is one of the central, most important mental functions. It has a decisive influence on such mental processes of children as observation, development of logical and figurative thinking, imagination, emotions. Stimulating general development, speech largely depends on it. Observation, the ability to notice characteristic features of objects and phenomena are formed in the process of speech development. Oral drawing, keeping observation diaries, excursions, widely used in teaching practice, serve this purpose.

It is also necessary to constantly work on instilling such qualities as imagery and emotionality in children's thinking and speech. "Imaginative thinking is associated with visual, concrete ideas. Therefore, in order to develop imagery in thinking, it is necessary to check more often how visual the students' ideas are." - wrote M.R. Lvov [4]. He advised asking students to visualize a particular picture or situation, to make picture plans, and to constantly work on pictorial techniques (comparisons, epithets, metaphors).

Conclusion.

Perception of the surrounding world, impressions obtained as a result of observation, reading in a book, form the basis for the work of the imagination. The development of students' imagination, like all other mental processes, occurs in activity. In speech development lessons, this activity is organized with the help of various oral and written exercises. The book by D. Rodari, "The Grammar of Fantasy" [6], tells about ways to develop imagination, how to help children compose based on it, "how to enliven and enrich with initiative the environment (at home and at school) in which the child grows up." It is based on the idea that "imagination is not the privilege of a few outstanding individuals, but that everyone is endowed with it."

Literatures:

1. Ladyzhenskaya T.A. System of work on the development of coherent speech of students. Moscow, 2015, 342 p.
2. Ladyzhenskaya T. A. et al. The system of teaching essays in grades V- VIII. Moscow, 2013. 424 p.
3. Ladyzhenskaya Sh. A., Novozhilova F.I. Oral and written statements of students on patriotic topics. // Russian language at school, 1997, No. 1. Pp. 26-28.
4. Lvov M.R. Methods of teaching Russian in elementary grades. - M., 2018. 524 p.
5. Mamushin V.E. On the development of the ability to improve the text. // Russian language at school, 2022, No. 2. P. 36-40
6. Rodari D. "Grammar of Fantasy". M., 2015.